

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIALOGUE-EXPERIENCE IN THE PRACTICE OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation. The article deals with the implementation of dialogue-experience in the practice. The development of technologies for the realization-experience dialogue in the practice of the educational process is carried out on the basis of: 1) clarifying the role of semantic experiences, participation in the processes of accumulation of meanings, their comparison and the generation of new meanings, primarily due to those encountered in the study of other people and oneself; personalization and personification, personal emotions of their implementation - in images, semantic structures and dispositions, as well as in direction;

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Clarification of the role of emotional-empathic, figurative and reflective experiences, recommendations for the semantic coordination of the semantic positions of the participants in the dialogue in terms of the frequency of cooperation in educational activities; their accidental emergence of interpersonal relations at the moment of "entry" into learning activity, and the transformation of the meaning of structural in the intergroup space also in the case of combined implementation-creative activity through the phenomena of the "reflected subject" - the image of the Other, the image of the perception of the Other, the personified image of the perception of the Other. In revealing the severity of emotional-empathic, figurative and reflective experiences of students, isolated and generalized technologies, grouped into three blocks, characterizing the directions of psychological,

psychological-pedagogical and pedagogical support of students in the educational process. In each block, technologies of a more random order are presented in three areas. Among them: the reduction of negative experiences, the restoration of "missing" experiences, the formation of positive experiences (a psychological block of technologies); personalized learning, team building technologies, reflective technologies (psychological and pedagogical block); technologies aimed at solving issues of contact, co-creation,

The relevance of the research topic is due, firstly, to the general problematics of the study of semantic communications, considered as a directed translation of meanings in the educational process. In psychological and pedagogical research, it is emphasized that modern high school students experience difficulties in communicating with classmates, teachers, parents, experience a state of psychological discomfort when realizing their essence, the semantic perspective of their education and personal self-determination. In the studies of O. E. Baitinger, D. N. Demidova, L. A. Regush and others, it is substantiated that the problems associated with a significant Other are experienced by respondents of adolescence and early youth as the most personally significant. Secondly, the relevance of the research topic being developed is due to the specifics of the dialogue in the semantic interpretation. Dialogue-experience refers to a special type of dialogues of semantic translation in the educational process [1, 19]. Its peculiarity lies in the fact that the experience carries out the semantic coordination of the positions of the participants in the dialogue interaction, their semantic coordination and transformation at all stages of educational activity and levels of communication [9, 21]. In dialogue, semantic experiences are involved in the accumulation of meanings (semantic induction), their comparison (semantic identification), as well as transformation (positioning of meaning) [7, 9]. These processes determine the presence of three structural levels in the dialogue-experience: pre-meaning, semantic and meta-

semantic. On each of them, the student uses personal ways of realizing the need for the social perception of other people, the need to be a person and be oneself [4].

At the pre-meaning level, these are images as harbingers of meanings. At the semantic level - semantic constructs and dispositions. At the metasense level - orientation. At each level of functioning of the dialogue-experience, the Other plays a special role [17]. At the pre-semantic level, in the process of semantic induction in the formation of a joint attitude to learning activity, there is the Other, or rather, its image, which made it possible to single out the “presence” component [3]. At the semantic level, in the process of semantic identification during the formation of interpersonal relations, an image of a significant Other arises, which made it possible to single out the “complicity” component [14]. At the metasense level, in the process of positing meanings in intergroup interaction, a personified image of a significant Other is involved, which made it possible to single out the “inclusion” component [7]. In the component composition of the model of dialogue-experience, the specificity of "personal contributions" is revealed. In the “presence” component, through the image of the Other as a kind of resource, the significance of the “personal contributions” of each participant in the dialogue for each other is realized [2]. In the “participation” component, through the image of a significant Other as a kind of identifier, the “personal contribution” of the Other “for me” is realized. In the “inclusion” component, through the personified image of a significant Other as a kind of transcendent, the significance of “me for Others” is realized. In the semantic agreement, coordination and transformation of the semantic positions of the participants in the dialogue-experience, specific emotional-empathic, figurative and reflexive experiences are actively involved. At the pre-meaning level, emotional-empathic experiences are represented by unconscious, actual experiences. Figurative experiences (images-archetypes) reflect the moment of formation of the image of the Other. Reflective experiences are connected with the learner's past experience.

At the semantic level, emotional and empathic experiences, basically, take on the character of an assessment - positivity and negativity. Figurative experiences (images-representations) are involved in the formation of the image of a significant Other. Reflective experiences reflect the current, actual state of the personality of students. At the metasense level, emotional-empathic experiences are revealed by existential experiences. Figurative experiences (images of creative imagination) provide the "construction" of a personified image of a significant Other. Reflective experiences reach the level of meta-reflection.

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